

IMPORTANCE OF SPIRITUALITY AND THE NATIONAL IDEA IN EDUCATING YOUNG PEOPLE

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Abstract. This study analyzes the role of the national idea in the process of spiritual growth and formation of a complete personality of young people from a philosophical perspective. The author recognizes the national idea as the main spiritual factor in educating the younger generation as morally perfect, patriotic, and socially responsible individuals. The aspects of the national idea that strengthen ideological stability, form spiritual immunity, and determine the model of a complete personality are scientifically illuminated.

Keywords: Spirituality, youth education, national idea, perfect person, spiritual growth, philosophical foundations, social responsibility, worldview.

Introduction

The system of spiritual education serves not only to form moral qualities in young people, but also to form in them metaphysical perception, that is, the ability to understand the meaning of existence. In this process, the national idea becomes the main philosophical mechanism that stabilizes moral ideals in society and unifies the system of values. Through the national idea, young people realize their life goals, understand the spiritual content of their actions. Ensuring this balance in Uzbek society is one of the central tasks of today's youth policy. Only young people who firmly know their national roots can keep up with secular thinking and not lose their spiritual and cultural place in global processes. The national idea occupies a central philosophical place in raising and educating the spirituality of young people. It is a force that unites society, leads the individual to perfection, and directs the nation towards sustainable development. The national idea shapes the thinking, moral criteria, and life position of young people. For young people, the national idea is not only an ideological program, but also an internal force that expresses their philosophy of life, identity, beliefs, and faith in the future. Consequently, organizing the spiritual education of young people on the basis of the national idea is a guarantee of social stability, spiritual revival, and philosophical renewal of Uzbekistan. The national idea plays a decisive role in ensuring the spiritual maturity of the younger generation. It not only strengthens

the ideological foundations of society, but also appears as a spiritual force that enriches the inner world of a person, calling him to goodness, patriotism, tolerance, and humanity. From this point of view, deeply instilling the national idea in the minds of young people and making it an integral part of the educational process is an urgent socio-pedagogical task. The national idea requires deeper scientific and practical study as the main ideological factor for enriching the content of the education and upbringing system, ensuring the spiritual well-being of young people, and educating them in the spirit of national values. The future, direction of development, and social stability of any society are determined, first of all, by its youth. In turn, the formation of a conscious, patriotic, spiritually and morally perfect and socially responsible young generation is closely related to the spiritual and political environment in society, national ideological foundations, and the soundness of the existing education system. After all, a society with high spirituality never declines. In the modern socio-spiritual environment, young people are influenced not only by the flow of information, but also by various foreign ideas, cultural pressure, and a consumerist worldview. In such conditions, it is an urgent task to educate them as comprehensively developed individuals who can withstand social crises, think independently, and rely on their cultural roots. This in itself requires the promotion of an educational philosophy that is inextricably linked with the national idea. The national idea is the sum of the historical memory, spiritual world, dreams and aspirations of the people, and life ideals. It is an internal ideological force that guides the process of a person's self-awareness and finding his place in society. Especially in the minds of the younger generation, this idea is not just a concept, but actively performs the function of spiritual and ideological immunity, social responsibility, aesthetic perception, and moral criterion. Therefore, without understanding the philosophical essence of the national idea, the upbringing of young people as perfect people will not be complete. The role of the national idea in shaping the modern thinking of young people is manifested in their value-based thinking, reliance on spiritual and moral criteria in decision-making, awareness of their identity, and a responsible approach to personal development. Such an approach ensures that the national idea becomes not only a theoretical but also a practical educational force.

The history of mankind over the past century testifies to the fact that among the peoples participating in such a process, there is mutual trust, cooperation, mutual respect and a desire to resolve conflicts on the basis of mutual understanding and agreement. A desire to enjoy the values and experience of each other's cultural achievements is formed. The tendency of peoples to unite with

each other forms a single, entire civilization, a planetary consciousness. That is, the harmony of nationality and universality is clearly manifested in world civilization and is included in the action program of the world community. Traditions and customs, as a social phenomenon, are based on the principles of stability and repetition of events occurring in various spheres of life. For many years, the formation of labor skills in the new generation, the regulation of the labor of young people have been an important task of traditions and customs. The national idea can be a means of educating spiritual beauty close to the heart. By awakening aesthetic consciousness, young people begin to understand the value of life, kindness, and elegance. Therefore, expressing the national idea in an aesthetic form is an elegant method of upbringing. The national idea should be instilled in the upbringing of young people not only through theoretical lectures, but also through various pedagogical methods. The following approaches are considered effective in today's educational methodology: Integral approach - teaching the national idea in harmony with such disciplines as history, literature, art, and philosophy. Project-based teaching - giving students the opportunity to develop films, presentations, essays, and social events based on the national idea. Educational debates - organizing lively conversations among young people on the topics of the national idea, globalism, and love for the homeland. Teaching based on real-life examples - showing the vital expression of the national idea with examples from the lives of historical figures and modern selfless people.

Conclusion

Through these methods, the national idea is instilled in the hearts of young people, their worldview is enriched, and the desire for perfection is awakened. In order to ensure the spiritual upliftment of young people and to deeply instill the national idea in pedagogical processes in shaping them as perfect people, the following recommendations can be put forward: Promoting the national idea in the mass media - creating content in a modern spirit about national values, patriotism, and perfection through social networks, podcasts, and TV series that are popular among young people. Developing methodological manuals for teachers - it is necessary to provide materials that include practical tasks, interactive exercises, and creative methods in teaching the national idea.

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